

12- Month PhD Report December 2021

PhD 05 - METAPRO

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(UCM)

Important Notes

- The full 9M report will be included in the Summary Progress Report due in September of each year.
- The full 12M report will be included in a new WP6 deliverable due in March of 2021/2022.
- A 'Summary' of each PhD project will be compiled from these 12M reports, and included in the Periodic report in February of each year.
 - The summary will be compiled from the content of the following sections :
 - Summary (approx. 500 words)
 - Overview of PhD progress
 - Deliverables and Milestones

1. Summary

During 2021 we managed to overcome a little bit the COVID situation to start making substantial progress on our tasks. We have been able to advance on the sampling process and also we achieved a strong bioinformatic pipeline that renders interesting results. The first part of the year has been mainly focused on the metagenomic analysis of the data from our own database, which offered interesting results that are guiding and shaping the next steps of the project. In addition, sequencing from the samples collected as part of this project has been performed and analysis are currently in process. We have been able to detect the main plazomicin resistant determinants, the 16S rRNA methyltransferases, from samples of very different origins. Furthermore, we also accomplished to determine their genetic surroundings, which is giving us hints of which bacteria may act as reservoir of these important resistance determinants. Therefore, this has led us to make some changes on some of the milestones of this project and in our workflow to be able to isolate these bacterial strains that are being the reservoir of the plazomicin resistance genes. However, there are still a lot of analyses ongoing and more COVID problems to overcome, but we are working hard to keep the track and end the project on the proposed dates.

2. Overview of the PhD project progress

- Spanish sampling design: since at the beginning we had some difficulties with the pandemic situation we had difficulties accessing sampling points, a metagenomic analysis of the data of previous projects from the lab was performed. In addition, samples from different ecological niches are already collected and we have established contact with other potential sampling points.
- Spanish sampling execution: samples from pig and poultry farms have been obtained and sampling for the rest of the ecological niches are undergoing.
- Metagenome sequencing of the Spanish sampling: sequencing of some of the samples has been performed and from the rest is currently being performed.
- Enterobacteria isolation and WGS from the first sampling: we are making a slight change in this task. We are no longer looking for just Enterobacteria, but we are aiming to isolate and culture the bacteria that act as a reservoir of the acquired 16S rRNA methyltransferases.
- Analysis of the genomic and metagenomic data from the Spanish sampling: we started some of the analysis using metagenomic data obtained in previous projects from the lab. We tested part of our pipeline and we were able to detect already acquired 16S rRNA methyltransferases with our read-based approach. Assembly-based approach is also giving us hints of where are these resistance mechanisms maintained in the different niches. Analysis from the sequence data of poultry and pig farms is being performed.
- Sampling design in the United Kingdom: contact with our UK partners has been established to discuss timeline and sampling possibilities.
- UK Sampling execution: this task is not due to take place until next year.
- Metagenome sequencing of the UK sampling: this task is not due to take place until next year.
- Enterobacteria isolation and WGS from the UK sampling: this task is not due to take place until next year.
- Analysis of the genomic and metagenomic data from the UK sampling: this task is not due to take place until next year.

- Writing of a guideline for early detection of plazomicin resistance determinants to preserve plazomicin for human clinical use: this task is not due to take place until June 2022.
- Writing of the Thesis manuscript: this task is not due to take place until June 2022.
- Thesis defence: this task is not due to take place until February 2023.

3. Progress of the research performed in the PhD project and key scientific results

During this year we continued with the metagenomic analysis of the data of pig and poultry farms from Spain belonging to previous projects. With a full metagenomic analysis we were able to detect 16S rRNA methyltransferases in a low prevalence in both types of farms using a read based approach. The 16S rRNA methyltransferase-positive samples were analysed as well with an assembly approach to study the potential genetic environment of the methyltransferases. It suggested that the Order *Eubacterium* may play a role in the maintenance of these resistance determinants. At present, we are extending this analysis to samples from pig and poultry farms across Europe to enlarge our dataset. We are also including human metagenomic data accessible via SRA to compare if we can detect 16S rRNA methyltransferases.

Since our metagenomic analysis suggest that the prevalence of 16S rRNA methyltransferases is low and associated to the Order *Eubacterium*, it is possible that in many samples we will not obtain enterobacteria via culturing. Therefore, we changed the milestone 4 (“Enterobacteria isolation and WGS from the first sampling”) to look for all the bacteria that may act as reservoirs of the plazomicin resistance. Currently, we are testing different culture media to isolate potential plazomicin resistant bacteria and proceed with their Whole Genome Sequencing to identify more accurately the genetic environment of the methyltransferases.

In addition, we were able to collect samples from a few different ecological niches. Some of them have been already sequenced and analyses of them will follow.

4. Progress of the research project: milestones and deliverables

Deliverables

PhD Project Reference	Deliverable number	Deliverable name	Delivery date from Annual Work Plan	Actual Delivery Date	If not achieved: Forecast achievement date	Comments
PhD05-AMR2/6.1/ETS-METAPRO	D-PhD05-4.1	Sampling questionnaire	JAN 2021	APR 2021		https://zenodo.org/record/4662681#.YMXl7JMzb0p

Milestones

PhD Project Reference	Milestone number	Milestone name	Delivery date from Annual Work Plan	Achieved (Yes / No)	If not achieved: Forecast achievement date	Comments
PhD5-AMR2/6.1/ET5-METAPRO	M3	Metagenome sequencing of the first sampling	MAR 2021	Partially	2022	We sequenced the first samples collected and sequencing the others that we are still collecting
	M4	Enterobacteria isolation and WGS from the first sampling	MAR 2021	No	2022	We made an adjustment to this milestone, so we are not longer for enterobacteria but we are looking for the bacteria that act as reservoir of plazomicin resistance determinants
	M5	Design of the second sampling	JUN 2021	No		Ongoing
	M6	Second sampling execution	SEP 2021	No		We expect to start in 2022 with this task
	M7	Metagenome sequencing of the second sampling	DEC 2021	No		We expect to start in 2022 with this task
	M8	Enterobacteria isolation and WGS from the second sampling	DEC 2021	No		We expect to start in 2022 with this task
	M9	Analysis of the genomic and metagenomic data from the first sampling	DEC 2021	No		We expect to start in 2022 with this task

5. Soft skills and Continuing Professional Development training

Name of Training Event	Topic	Dates (DD/MM/YY)	Organising Institute
MicroMundo Symposium	AMR	27-28 th /04/2021	Universidad Complutense de Madrid
Webinar Series 'Jornadas sobre la Carrera Investigadora'	Scientific Research	14 th /01/2021 – 29 th /04/2021	Universidad Complutense de Madrid
Course 'Hojas de Cálculo con Excel I'	Excel	15 th /03/2021 – 30 th /06/2021	Universidad Complutense de Madrid
Course 'Hojas de Cálculo con Excel II'	Excel	14 th /06/2021 – 29 th /10/2021	Universidad Complutense de Madrid
Workshop 'Bioinformatics tools and methods for antimicrobial resistance'	AMR	15 th /10/2021	PH4GE, JPIAMR and CLIMB-BIG-DATA
BioinfoCAM meeting	Bioinformatics	21 st /10/2021	SEBiBC

6. Publications and additional outputs

Publications

Proceedings of the 3rd Annual Scientific Meeting of the One Health European Joint Programme on Foodborne Zoonoses, Antimicrobial Resistance and Emerging Threats. Copenhagen (Denmark)/Online meeting, June 9th - 11th, 2021, page 132

Bosco R. Matamoros, Roberto M. La Ragione, & Bruno Gonzalez-Zorn. (2021). Questionnaire on farm management, biosecurity, health and antibiotic use in livestock farming (METAPRO_D-PhD05-4.1). Zenodo. DOI: 10.5281/zenodo.4662680

Proceedings of the 31st European Congress of Clinical Microbiology and Infectious Diseases (ECCMID). Online Congress, 9th – 12th July, 2021, page 200

Proceedings of the XXVIII Congreso de la Sociedad Española de Microbiología (SEM). Online Congress, 28th June – 2nd July, 2021, page 214

Additional output

7. Remarkable outcomes

8. Impact & relevance

This PhD project connects three major laboratories focused on the fight of Antimicrobial Resistance, having all of them participated in other European Projects in the past. This offers a possibility to maintain the great relationship that has been always present between institutes. This fact is highlighted by the various exchanges of students that have had part and how successful they have been. In addition, since the PhD project supervisors study AMR from different perspectives, this new collaboration brings the opportunity to combine them all together to get the most out of it. But it is not only limited to that. Being part of the OHEJP networks allows to connect the partners and the student with different backgrounds and perspectives that are often needed.

9. Follow-up of the recommendations and comments in previous review(s) by the Ethics Advisors

The responses to previous ethical reviewers comments have been accepted and this is closed.

10. Impact of COVID-19 crisis on the project

Tasks or Subtasks			Milestones and Deliverables				Associated budget	
Name of Task or Subtask	End date according to AWP 2020	Expected end date due to crisis	Associated Milestone or Deliverable	Deadline according to AWP 2020	New proposed deadline	Reason for delay	Budget that will not be spent	Budget that will be spent with delay

Comments:

11. List of critical risks

Description of risk	Yes/No
Loss of PhD supervisor(s)	No
Loss of technical training staff delaying progress of the work	No
Delay in work plan execution	Yes
Conflicts between the collaborative partners that support the PhD	No
Lack of commitment between the collaborative partners that support the PhD	No
Delay in duties, tasks or reporting	Yes
Poor working relationships within the PhD project team	No
Change in PhD student circumstances requiring temporary leave	No
Other risks (please describe)	No

Additional information:

12. Interactions with on-going JRPs/JIPs or with external (EU or national) relevant projects or initiatives such as national action plans (AMR, Zoonoses etc.), OHEJP stakeholders, national and international surveillance programmes.

FARMED: Fast Antimicrobial Resistance and Mobile-Element Detection using metagenomics for animal and human on-site tests (<https://onehealthjep.eu/jrp-farmed/>). Since the objectives and the techniques of both projects are similar, the candidate is taking part actively in the tasks performed at UCM associated to this project.

EFFORT: Ecology from Farm to Fork Of microbial drug Resistance and Transmission (<http://www.effort-against-amr.eu/>). The group participated actively in the EFFORT project and its activities and resources are the foundation of the present research project.

JPIAMR: Joint Programming Initiative on Antimicrobial Resistance. The lab is part of the NEAR-AMR (<https://www.jpiamr.eu/near-amr/>) and of the GAP-ONE (<https://www.jpiamr.eu/gap-one/>) projects. The candidate can benefit of these networks to extend the search of plazomicin resistance determinants in other parts of Europe and Africa or to estimate the economic burden of plazomicin resistance.

AVANT: Alternatives to Veterinary Antimicrobials (<https://avant-project.eu/>). The student will also be involved in the development and test of alternatives to antimicrobials.

DAMR-Una Europa: "Disseminate antimicrobial resistance knowledge and the use of whole genome sequencing on relevant bacterial pathogens during COVID-19 world emergency" (<https://www.una-europa.eu/>). The student is taking part in this project teaching a webinar on metagenomics and collaborating on the sequencing of bacterial pathogens.

13. List of dissemination and communication activities

Name of the activity:	<i>OHEJP Three Minute Competition 2021 and poster presentation</i>		
Date:	<i>10th June 2021</i>		
Place:	<i>Copenhagen/ONLINE</i>		
Specify the Dissemination and Communication activities linked to the One Health EJP project for each of the			
	Yes / No		Yes / No
<i>Organisation of a Conference</i>		<i>Participation to a Conference</i>	X
<i>Organisation of a Workshop</i>		<i>Participation to a Workshop</i>	
<i>Press release</i>		<i>Participation to an Event other than a</i>	
<i>Non-scientific and non-peer-reviewed publication</i>		<i>Video/Film</i>	
<i>Exhibition</i>		<i>Brokerage Event</i>	
<i>Flyer</i>		<i>Pitch Event</i>	X
<i>Training</i>		<i>Trade Fair</i>	
<i>Social Media</i>		<i>Participation in activities organized jointly</i>	
<i>Website</i>		<i>Other</i>	
<i>Communication Campaign (e.g. Radio, TV)</i>			
Specify the estimated number of persons reached, in the context of this dissemination and communication			
	Number		Number
<i>Scientific Community (Higher Education,</i>	<i>550+</i>	<i>Media</i>	
<i>Industry</i>		<i>Investors</i>	
<i>Civil Society</i>		<i>Customers</i>	
<i>General Public</i>		<i>Other</i>	
<i>Policy Makers</i>			

Name of the activity:	<i>Seminar presentation 'Identificación y caracterización molecular de mecanismos de resistencia a antibióticos emergentes'</i>		
Date:	<i>12th May 2021</i>		
Place:	<i>Faculty of Veterinary Medicine, Universidad Complutense de Madrid</i>		
Specify the Dissemination and Communication activities linked to the One Health EJP project for each of the			
	Yes / No		Yes / No
<i>Organisation of a Conference</i>		<i>Participation to a Conference</i>	
<i>Organisation of a Workshop</i>		<i>Participation to a Workshop</i>	
<i>Press release</i>		<i>Participation to an Event other than a</i>	X
<i>Non-scientific and non-peer-reviewed publication</i>		<i>Video/Film</i>	
<i>Exhibition</i>		<i>Brokerage Event</i>	
<i>Flyer</i>		<i>Pitch Event</i>	
<i>Training</i>		<i>Trade Fair</i>	
<i>Social Media</i>		<i>Participation in activities organized jointly</i>	
<i>Website</i>		<i>Other</i>	
<i>Communication Campaign (e.g. Radio, TV)</i>			
Specify the estimated number of persons reached, in the context of this dissemination and communication			
	Number		Number
<i>Scientific Community (Higher Education,</i>	<i>50+</i>	<i>Media</i>	
<i>Industry</i>		<i>Investors</i>	
<i>Civil Society</i>		<i>Customers</i>	
<i>General Public</i>		<i>Other</i>	
<i>Policy Makers</i>			

Name of the activity:	31 st European Congress of Clinical Microbiology and Infectious Diseases (ECCMID) + Poster Presentation		
Date:	9 th - 12 th July 2021		
Place:	ONLINE		
Specify the Dissemination and Communication activities linked to the One Health EJP project for each of the			
	Yes / No		Yes / No
Organisation of a Conference		Participation to a Conference	X
Organisation of a Workshop		Participation to a Workshop	
Press release		Participation to an Event other than a	
Non-scientific and non-peer-reviewed publication		Video/Film	
Exhibition		Brokerage Event	
Flyer		Pitch Event	
Training		Trade Fair	
Social Media		Participation in activities organized jointly	
Website		Other	
Communication Campaign (e.g. Radio, TV)			
Specify the estimated number of persons reached, in the context of this dissemination and communication			
	Number		Number
Scientific Community (Higher Education,	14000+	Media	
Industry		Investors	
Civil Society		Customers	
General Public		Other	
Policy Makers			

Name of the activity:	XXVIII Congreso de la Sociedad Española de Microbiología (SEM) + Poster Presentation		
Date:	28 th June – 2 nd July 2021		
Place:	ONLINE		
Specify the Dissemination and Communication activities linked to the One Health EJP project for each of the			
	Yes / No		Yes / No
Organisation of a Conference		Participation to a Conference	X
Organisation of a Workshop		Participation to a Workshop	
Press release		Participation to an Event other than a	
Non-scientific and non-peer-reviewed publication		Video/Film	
Exhibition		Brokerage Event	
Flyer		Pitch Event	
Training		Trade Fair	
Social Media		Participation in activities organized jointly	
Website		Other	
Communication Campaign (e.g. Radio, TV)			
Specify the estimated number of persons reached, in the context of this dissemination and communication			
	Number		Number
Scientific Community (Higher Education,	900+	Media	
Industry		Investors	
Civil Society		Customers	
General Public		Other	
Policy Makers			

